

AN OUTLINE GRAMMAR OF THE TEPERA DIALECT OF TABLA, A NON-AUSTRONESIAN LANGUAGE OF IRIAN JAYA (WEST NEW GUINEA)

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The text of this outline grammar is essentially unchanged from the version of May 1985. I have not had the opportunity to work on Tepera since then, and am making the current version available as I do not know when or if I will be able to return to work on this language. I have done some reformatting and corrected some typographical and similar errors. Bibliographical references have been updated for Collier & Collier (1986) and for Collier & Gregerson (1985). Demographic data in §1 have been updated where appropriate to match the published sources, but remain 40–50 years old. The area where Tepera is spoken is now (May 2024) administratively in Papua Province, Indonesia. Tepera falls under the following language codes: ISO 639-3: tnm; Glottocode: tabl1243.

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The corresponding in-text citation would be: Comrie & Jakarimilena (1985).

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This outline grammar owes an unrepayable debt to Nico Jakarimilena, who put his native intuitions about Tepera unstintingly at the disposal of the author. In addition, members of Mr. Jakarimilena's family provided recordings of texts in the Tepera dialect, which form a second source for the generalizations made in this grammar. Kenneth Collier, of the Irian Jaya branch of the Summer Institute of Linguistics, kindly put at my disposal his materials (texts and articles) on the closely related Yewena dialect.

1. Introduction

The Tabla language is one of the non-Austronesian (Papuan) languages of the Indonesian province of Irian Jaya (the western half of the island of New Guinea), spoken in the area of Tanah Merah, to the west of the provincial capital of Jayapura. The language was formerly also known as Tanah Merah, but since this name is also used for another language, I have avoided the older name here. According to the 1973 census, the total number of speakers of Tabla was about 3,500, this figure apparently including the three dialects Tepera, Yewena, and Yongsu, but not Yakari, which, though clearly closely related genetically to Tabla, is apparently considered a separate language (Jakarimilena 1979: 1–3). Collier & Collier (1986: 16) estimate the total number of speakers for Tabla, including Yakari (Yokari), as approximately 3,700.

Although the language name Tabla is an Indonesianized form of the word *Tepera* (i.e. /təpə'ra/), the name Tepera is used here, as in the other publications cited, specifically for this dialect, which according to Collier & Collier (1986: 16) has approximately 800 speakers. The three dialects Tepera, Yewena, and Yongsu are very closely related and mutually intelligible. The present account is concerned solely with Tepera, although occasional comparative references are made to the Yewena dialect, at present the subject of active study by Collier et al. Tepera is spoken in the villages of Tablanusu (indigenous name *tepera o nusu*), Depapre (indigenous name *tepera waw na*), and Tablasufa (indigenous name *tepera suwa*); see the map at the end of this outline, from Jakarimilena (1979).

Tepera is a member of the Sentani language family, of which the language called Sentani is the best known representative, having been the subject of a monograph by Cowan (1965). The genetic relation of Sentani and Tepera will be obvious from even a superficial perusal of this monograph and of Cowan (1965); the western dialect of Sentani is, incidentally, closer to Tepera than the eastern dialect described by Cowan. The wider genetic affiliations of the Sentani family are speculative – beyond the fact that it is non-Austronesian (Papuan) – and since I have not investigated this problem I will make no further claims here.

The Tabla language, and more specifically the Tepera dialect, are currently undergoing replacement by Bahasa Indonesia (Indonesian, Malay), so that the younger generation is often more at home in Bahasa Indonesia, or at least the Irian variety of Bahasa Indonesia, than in their local dialect of Tabla; a major factor here is the use of Bahasa Indonesia as lingua franca among speakers of different indigenous languages, so that in marriages between speakers of different languages, for instance, Bahasa Indonesia is often the only language in common, and Bahasa Indonesia therefore becomes the language of the household and ultimately the first or only language of the children. It should be noted that the use of Bahasa Indonesia as lingua franca in Irian Jaya predates the incorporation of

Irian Jaya into Indonesia, having been encouraged by the Dutch colonial authorities in what was then Netherlands New Guinea.

My principal native-speaker consultant, Nico Jakarimilena (at the time a graduate student at the University of Southern California), is a native speaker of Tepera, but considers that his command of the language is now passive, having been replaced as his basic active medium by Bahasa Indonesia. His familiarity with other dialects of Tabla also makes him sometimes unsure about the genuineness of forms for the Tepera dialect. Since Mr. Jakarimilena is the only Tepera speaker with whom I have been able to work at first hand, this obviously places certain limitations on the present study. However, in addition to work with Mr. Jakarimilena, I have also had access to recordings of traditional stories made by Mr. Jakarimilena's relatives, who are active first-language speakers of Tepera. Wherever possible, I have tried to corroborate claims based on elicitation with reference to these texts. I plan to prepare these texts for distribution in the near future.

There has been very little previous work on Tabla. For the Tepera dialect, the main previous study is Jakarimilena (1979), which concentrates on the nominal (including pronominal) morphology. For the Yewena dialect, there are studies on the phonology (Collier & Collier 1986), on the morphology of the verb (Collier & Gregerson 1985) – this study on the verb has been particularly invaluable in my work on Tepera – and on the use of aspectual oppositions in indicating foregrounded and backgrounded material in narrative (Collier, n.d.). While I have gained many insights from this work on Yewena, and have made occasional references to differences between Yewena and Tepera in the text, I am aware that these are different dialects, so that material from the one cannot be carried over to the other without checking. The morphological material on Tepera in Jakarimilena (1979) has been incorporated into the present study, which is why I insist that the present study has been carried out in collaboration with Nico Jakarimilena as an active participant.

2. Phonology

Vowels

The vowel system of Tepera may be represented by the following chart:

	Front	Central	Back
High	i		u
Mid	é	e	o
Low		a	

Note that the back vowels are rounded, while the front and central vowels are unrounded. Here and below, I use an orthography based on that of Bahasa Indonesia, including the distinction between *e* and *é*.

While some instances of *e* are derived (by epenthesis, or by apophony of *a*), there are nonetheless many remaining instances of *e* contrasting with zero or with other vowels, e.g. *aw* ‘lime (chewed with betelnut)’, *awe* ‘bird’; *da* ‘this’, *di* ‘that’, *do* ‘male’, *de* ‘I’; *éré* ‘skin’, *éru* ‘testicle’, *ére* ‘fence’.

There is little allophonic variation for the five vowels *a*, *é*, *i*, *o*, *u*, although *é*, *o*, *i*, *u* are somewhat lower before a syllable-final nasal, and *é*, *o* are somewhat higher before syllable-final *y* and somewhat lower before syllable-final *w*. The vowel *e* is likely to be raised and fronted in the the neighborhood of front vowels or *y*, and to be rounded in the neighborhood of rounded vowels or labial consonants (including *w*).

Consonants

The following table gives the phonetic values of the symbols with which I operate in this monograph. However, this transcription involves more controversial analyses than was the case with the vowels, so that the chart should be studied in connection with the notes below.

	Bilabial	Alveolar	Palatal	Velar
Voiceless stop	p	t		k
Voiced stop	b	d	j	
Voiceless fricative		s	sy	
Tap		r		
Nasal	m	n	ny	(ng)
Semivowel	w		y	

Apart from the details discussed below, there is little allophonic variation.

Labials: The labials are labialized (i.e. have lip-rounding) before rounded vowels and schwa. In some instances the labialization is so marked that phonetically one has a diphthong in the preceding syllable, e.g. in aorist verb forms in *pe-k*: thus *meko-pe-k-o* ‘make-Ø-AOR-3SG’ is phonetically often almost [me'kowpwuko].

Alveolars: *t*, *d* seem to be dental rather than alveolar.

Palatals: I consider these to be unit phonemes, rather than sequences of alveolar and palatal semivowel. One reason is the otherwise unexplained absence of the voiceless palatal stop *c* (other than in loans from Bahasa Indonesia). The other is my claim below that syllable-initial consonant clusters are in general nonphonotactic in Tepera.

Voiceless stops: The voiceless bilabial stop is in free variation with a voiceless bilabial fricative. In general, any word is acceptable with either stop or fricative pronunciation, although in practice some words seem to have been institutionalized with one pronunciation or the other: this is usually the stop, although the greeting *poy* invariably

has an initial fricative (whereas *poy* ‘good’, from which it derives, varies between initial stop and fricative). In one of the recorded texts, *Pisyo* ‘flying fish’, the word *pisyo* is regularly pronounced with an initial fricative.

There is no phonemic glottal stop in Tepera, although a phonetic glottal stop may occur at the end of any word otherwise ending in a vowel. In sentence-stressed monosyllables ending in a vowel and occurring prepausally, there are two possible pronunciations: either there is a final glottal stop, or the vowel is lengthened.

Voiced stops: The main problem of analysis here is the relation between nonprenasalized and prenasalized voiced stops. In general, nonprenasalized voiced stops occur word initially (which includes initial position in the second component of a compound), while prenasalized voiced stops occur elsewhere. This is a common pattern in languages of New Guinea, where the two series are allophones. However, there are some problems for this analysis in Tepera. Loans from Bahasa Indonesia have nonprenasalized voiced stops even word medially, e.g. *adat* ‘tradition’, but presumably this could readily be taken care of by partitioning the lexicon into native and foreign lexical items. More significantly, some native words have word medial nonprenasalized voiced stops, including words where there does not seem to be any motivation for treating the word as a compound, e.g. *kabutu* ‘kind of bag’; there is even a minimal pair: *seduku* ‘he hung (transitive)’, *senduku* ‘it was attached’. There is one word which frequently has an initial prenasalized voiced stop even in isolation, namely *mbéy* ‘one’ (which can also be pronounced as *béy* when not following a consonant-final word; incidentally, the Sentani pronunciation *embéy* is not possible in Tepera, which does not permit word-initial *e*). There are also examples where the prenasalized voiced stop occurs even though there would appear to be an intervening word boundary, as can be seen from comparing *day te* ‘immediately’ and *ne nday te* ‘again’. Given that Tepera allows a syllable-final nasal (assimilated to the point of articulation of a following consonant) and allows syllable-initial voiced stops, one would expect that the sequences *mb*, *nd* would arise from the adjacency of two segments across a syllable boundary, in addition to any allophonic variation between nonprenasalized and prenasalized voiced stops. Because of these complications, I have decided to make use of an orthography that systematically records the difference between nonprenasalized and prenasalized voiced stops, the latter represented as *mb*, *nd*.

Nasals: Syllable-finally, only one nasal occurs in Tepera, phonetically velar, except that it assimilates to the place of articulation of a following consonant. I have represented this syllable-final nasal as *ng*, except where it has some other value by nasal assimilation within the word. Nasal assimilation also takes place optionally across word boundaries where adjacent words are closely related (e.g. parts of a compound, a noun and following case marker): the syllable-final nasal is deleted before a word-initial nasal, assimilates in place of articulation to a word-initial *p*, *b*, *t*, *d*, *s*, while before *r*, *w*, *y* the syllable-final nasal is realized as nasalization of the vowel.

Semivowels: I have departed from Bahasa Indonesia orthographic principles, and also from the orthography used for Yewena by Collier et al., by writing the semivowels as *w*, *y* not only syllable initially but also syllable finally. I believe that this provides a better fit with the phonemic analysis, although for a practical orthography it would probably be preferable to follow the principles of Bahasa Indonesia orthography.

Bahasa Indonesia loan phonemes: In loans from Bahasa Indonesia (BI), the phonemes *c*, *g*, *l* may occur, i.e. a voiceless palatal stop, a voiced velar stop, and a lateral frictionless continuant. They are often replaced by closely corresponding Tepera sounds, namely *sy*, *k*, *r* respectively, e.g. *syuma* ‘only’ (BI *cuma*), *kuru* ‘teacher’ (BI *guru*), *sekora* ‘school’ (BI *sekola*). These substitutions are also found where the result would be nonphonotactic in Tepera, e.g. *kapar* ‘ship’ (BI *kapal*).

Syllable structure

The basic syllable structure in Tepera is (C)V(G/N), where C = consonant, V = vowel, G = semivowel (glide), and N = nasal. Syllables with the apparent structure CVGN are also possible, though only in words where there is good reason for supposing that the nasal component is part of an initial voiced stop in the following syllable, e.g. *mekonaymbonde* ‘they will make’; I assume that the syllabification is in fact ...*nay-mbo*.... Examples of the permitted syllable structures are: *éti* ‘tooth’, *péw* ‘tongue’, *dong* ‘egg’, *berengka* ‘head’.

Vowel-initial syllables apparently occur only word-initially, and *e* is excluded from this position. This means that vowel hiatus is not possible word-medially. Some instances of apparent hiatus I analyze as having an intervening semivowel, which is a possible pronunciation, e.g. *niyang* ‘salamander’.

Phonetically, syllable-initial consonant clusters do occur, but I assume that these are due to the omission of *e* in normal-rate speech, i.e. phonetic *bringké* ‘cold’ corresponds to *beringké*. In most instances the pronunciation with schwa is also possible, though there are some instances where Mr. Jakarimilena rejects this pronunciation, e.g. *merway* (unacceptable **mereway*) ‘river’, so that there remains a small residue of problems.

Loans from Bahasa Indonesia, incidentally, frequently violate the phonotactic constraints of Tepera; the speakers I have listened to seem to have no problems in pronouncing these nonphonotactic items.

Stress

The basic stress rules in Tepera seem to be the following: (i) monosyllables are stressed on their only vowel; (ii) disyllables are stressed on their initial syllable, e.g. *éti* ‘tooth’, *'sese* ‘grandfather’, *'neka* ‘his elder sibling’; (iii) words of more than two syllables are stressed on their penultimate syllable, unless this contains the vowel *e*, in which case the

stress falls on the antepenultimate syllable, e.g. *sen'sori* 'lake', *yésere* 'belly', *'sekeré* 'louse'.

The components of a compound are stressed separately, e.g. *'dari+'do* 'kind of cloud', literally 'land male'. (I use '+' to separate the components of a compound.)

There are, however, numerous exceptions to the general stress rule, and a fuller study is clearly merited. Examples of exceptions include *mi'r'é* 'female', and the dialect name *tepe'ra* 'Tepera'.

It should be noted that stress is one of the criteria used below in establishing word boundaries, in particular in treating the case markers of nouns as separate words but the inflections of verbs as part of the same word as the verb stem. Even here, however, there are certain problems: thus, the demonstratives *da* 'this' and *di* 'that' and the locative postposition *ne* normally function as separate words, but the expressions *'da pe ne* 'here' (literally 'this place LOC') and *'di pe ne* 'there' (and the directional equivalents with *te* for *ne* and the source equivalents with *re*) are stressed as indicated, as if one word.

Phonological rules

In addition to phonological rules implied by the discussion above, there is evidence for the following rules, especially in verb morphology (essentially the only area in Tepera where there are productive morphophonemic alternations); a more abstract approach to verb morphology would require further rules, as in Collier & Gregerson (1985).

Vowel apocope: Where two vowels would otherwise occur in hiatus, the first is lost, e.g. underlying /te + are/ 'see-1SG' gives *t-are*.

Glide insertion: In one case – the second person singular of the present tense – instead of the first vowel being deleted to avoid hiatus, the semivowel *y* is inserted, e.g. *meko-y-é* 'you make'.

Desyllabification: Another exception to apocope is that in negative and conditional forms, *i* becomes *y* after a vowel other than *e* or *i*, e.g. *meko-ypay* 'not make' (cf. *an-ipay* 'not eat' from *ane-*, and *ipay* 'not go' from \emptyset -).

Apophony: Where the vowel /a/ ends up in the syllable immediately preceding another syllable with /a/, the first /a/ shifts to *e*, e.g. /sane + are/ 'say-1SG' gives *sen-are*. All the examples I have of apophony are in the initial syllable. It is possible that /o/ may also undergo apophony.

Tap/stop alternation: There is some evidence for alternation between the intervocalic tap *r* and the the voiced stop *d* elsewhere (word initially and after a nasal), e.g. *de-r-éy* 'my' (cf. *we-w-éy* 'your', *ne-n-éy* 'his').

Vowel split: In verb forms with an object prefix (always a single consonant) preceding a subject suffix, the initial vowel of the subject suffix is copied before the object suffix, e.g. *i-k-a-n-are* ‘I gave it to him’ (literally ‘give-AOR-a-3SGO-1SG’).

Schwa insertion/deletion: There are some instances of schwa/Ø alternations, providing evidence for a rule or rules of schwa insertion and/or deletion. Some instances of schwa deletion could be treated under the general vowel apocope rule, e.g. the fact that the object prefixes consist of only a consonant before a vowel but of a consonant plus schwa elsewhere: compare *sane-yo-w-ne* ‘he told him’ (literally ‘say-IMP-3SG-3SGO’) with *i-k-a-n-are* ‘I gave him’. The word-final schwa of verb forms is deleted after a semivowel if there is a following object suffix or the relative postposition *na*, e.g. *sane-yo-w-ne* ‘he told him’, *sane-yo-w na* ‘his saying’ (cf. *sane-yo-we* ‘he said’).

3. Morphology and syntax

Rather than following the traditional division into morphology followed by syntax, I have chosen to combine the two, since otherwise arbitrary divisions are required (for instance, treating forms in one section but their uses in a section far separated from the discussion of forms).

Basic notions

Tepera is a rigidly verbfinal language, as is common among Papuan languages. It has most of the other properties one would expect to find cooccurring with verbfinal word order, i.e. it is basically a headfinal language. The main exception is that adjectives (and numerals) follow their head noun. Word order within phrases is fixed, though word order within the clause is relatively free, subject only to the verb-final requirement.

The role of noun phrases within the clause is indicated primarily by postpositions, and postpositions are also the prime means of indicating possessive relations within the noun phrase. Nominals have little morphology: some kinship terms have special possessed forms; the comitative of pronouns is perhaps to be regarded as an inflectional form (e.g. *dembere* ‘with me’, cf. *de* ‘I’ – nouns take the postposition *pere* to express this relation); the possessive of pronouns (e.g. *deréy* ‘my’) is also probably inflectional; otherwise nominal relations are expressed analytically.

Verb morphology is complex, and involves primarily exclusively suffixation (at least for inflectional morphology). In the research leading up to this monograph some progress has been made in studying the inflectional morphology of the verb; no serious study has been attempted yet, however, of derivational morphology. In addition to showing tense-aspect-mood, verbs agree in person and number with their subject, and some transitive verbs also agree with their object.

There appear to be no grammatical relation changing rules in Tepera, comparable to passivization in English; this feature is common among Papuan languages.

Clauses can be combined into larger sentences either by simple juxtaposition, or by means of conjunctions (in fact, often identical to postpositions) that appear after the verb of the subordinate clause. Most subordinate clauses precede the main clause on which they are dependent. Relative clauses may either precede or follow their head noun. Unlike some Highland languages, Tepera does not have special medial verb forms, i.e. verb forms that can only be used in dependent clauses. Clause-initial conjunctions are also found, but these are all loans from Bahasa Indonesia and represent the most obvious syntactic influence of Bahasa Indonesia on Tepera.

Constituent order within the clause

Tepera is a rigidly verbfinal language. This is true both of elicited material and of textual material. The normal order is Subject – Object – Verb, as in:

- (1) de (ye) di detero te pene-y-are.
I (INST) that person OBJ hit-IMP-1SG
'I was hitting that person.'

It is, however, possible for objects to be placed clause-initially, for purposes of topicalization, as in:

- (2) di detero (te) de (ye) pene-y-are.

Note that it is common to omit the object postposition from a preposed object.

Among object noun phrases, the direct object normally precedes the indirect object (alternatively: the patient precedes the recipient). Adverbials are freer in their positioning, always subject to the verbfinal constraint.

Most clauses, incidentally, do contain a verb, although nonverbal predicates are also possible. In particular, predicate adjectives, nouns, and adverbials typically occur with no verb, as in:

- (3) ne miré pe poy.
the female TOP good
'The woman is good.'
- (4) ne miré pe kuru.
the female TOP teacher
'The woman is a teacher.'

(5) ne miré pe da pe ne.
 the female TOP this place LOC
 ‘The woman is here.’

Such nonverbal predicates cannot express verbal categories; this includes not only subject agreement, but also tense-aspect-mood and polarity. If it is necessary to give overt expression to tense-aspect-mood or polarity, then the verb *neke-* ‘stay’ is used, and it requires a noun phrase complement to take the object postposition *te*:

(6) di detero pe kuru te neke-yo-we.
 that person TOP teacher OBJ stay-IMP-3SG
 ‘That person was a teacher.’

Note that the subjects of sentences with adjectival, nominal, or adverbial predicates normally have the topic marker *pe* on the subject, especially if there is no verb.

Syntactic-semantic relations of noun phrases within the clause

The syntactic-semantic relations of noun phrases within the clause are expressed primarily by means of postpositions, the major ones of which are discussed below. Except where indicated otherwise, the postpositions are the same for all noun phrases, including personal pronouns.

Subject: Most commonly, the subject takes no postposition. If the subject is also a topic, then it can take the topic postposition *pe*; although the topic postposition occurs most frequently with subjects, it can also occur with preposed objects (which then lose the object marker *te*). Subjects can also take the instrumental postposition *ye*; when this postposition is used, the subject is focus of its clause, i.e. represents the most essential new information communicated by that clause.

Direct and indirect object: These are both indicated by means of the object (OBJ) postposition *te*. This postposition is particularly multifunctional, since it can also indicate direction (see below). The use of *te* to mark direct and indirect objects is illustrated in:

(7) de ye kabutu te miré te i-k-a-n-are.
 I INST bag OBJ woman OBJ give-AOR-Ø-3SGO-1SG
 ‘I gave the bag to the woman.’

Note that the use of the terms direct and indirect object here follows their applicability to English, and does not necessarily reflect the reality of Tepera. The only rule in Tepera that I am aware of that specifically refers to a single class of objects is object verb agreement: some transitive verbs agree with one of their objects. For ditransitive verbs, this agreement is invariably with the notional recipient, not the patient. In the texts, and occasionally in elicitation, there are direct objects (other than topicalized direct objects)

lacking the postposition *te*; I am not aware of the conditioning factors (insertion of *te* is usually also considered grammatical), although one generalization seems to be that the postposition is not omissible with indirect objects (recipients).

Instrumental: The instrumental (INST) function is indicated by means of the postposition *ye*. Exactly the same postposition is used to mark some subjects, namely those in focus (see above). However, despite the morphological identity, the syntactic functions are clearly distinct: a subject noun phrase marked with *ye* continues to trigger subject verb agreement, just like any other subject; an instrumental noun phrase marked with *ye* never triggers verb agreement.

Direction: Place to which is indicated by the postposition *te*, the same as is used for direct and indirect objects. I have used the gloss OBJ (for object) for all instances of this postposition. Note that expressions of direction, unlike direct and indirect object, never trigger object verb agreement. An example is *miyé te* ‘to the house’.

Location: Place at which is indicated by the locative (LOC) postposition *ne*, e.g. *miyé ne* ‘in the house’.

Source: Place from which is indicated by the ablative (ABL) postposition *re*, e.g. *miyé re* ‘from the house’.

Comitative: Accompaniment is expressed by means of the comitative (COM) postposition *pere*, e.g. *miré pere* ‘(together] with the woman’. Although personal pronouns in general take exactly the same postpositions as other nouns, their comitatives are exceptional: *de-mbere* ‘with me’, etc.; since prenasalized stops normally only occur word medially, there is some motivation for regarding the pronominal comitative marker *-mbere* as a suffix, despite its obvious similarity to *pere*. A common way of expressing a conjoined noun phrase is *NP₁ pere NP₂ pere* ‘NP₁ and NP₂’.

Cause: The postposition *sate* indicates cause, e.g. *su sate* ‘because of the sun’. This postposition, together with some of the more specific locational postpositions, is perhaps to be analyzed rather as a kind of possessive construction: there is a noun *sa*, with very general meaning (‘thing’), and perhaps this postposition is actually *sa te*, the preceding noun being an unmarked possessor.

The more specific locational postpositions clearly involve a kind of possessive construction: the structure is Noun + Locational noun + Postposition, where the locational nouns are simply nouns that happen to have locational meaning, e.g. *bura* ‘space on, above’, *kere* ‘space under’, *yé* ‘space by the side of’, *da su* ‘this side’, *di su* ‘that side’. Examples are: *oru bura ne* ‘on the rock’, *merway di su te* ‘to that side of the river’, *o kere re* ‘from under the tree’.

Benefactives: Because of certain problems in the analysis of benefactives, they are treated in a separate section below.

Internal structure of the noun phrase

Tepera noun phrases are basically right-headed, except that adjectives (and numerals) follow the head noun and relative clauses may do so. In general, there is no agreement between the constituents of a noun phrase, the postposition occurring at the far right of the whole noun phrase. For exceptions with relative clauses, see the section on clause combining below. For benefactives, see the relevant section below.

Noun phrases in Tepera may be headless, i.e. consist solely of an adjective or a possessive, e.g. *poy* ‘a good one’, *de na* ‘mine’. Postpositions follow such noun phrases in the same way as for headed noun phrases, i.e. their object forms are *poy te*, *de na te*.

Demonstratives precede the head noun, the demonstratives being *ne* ‘the (aforementioned)’, *da* ‘this’, *di* ‘that’, e.g. *ne/da/di awe* ‘the/this/that bird’.

Adjectives (and numerals – see the section on numerals below) follow their head noun, e.g. *awe poy* ‘good bird’. Note that a postposition follows the whole noun phrase, i.e. the object form of ‘a good bird’ is *awe poy te*. Attributes derived from nouns by means of the postposition *na*, though functioning in many ways as adjectives, are syntactically possessors, and therefore precede the head noun, as noted in the section on possession below.

Numerals

The Tepera numeral system has basic numerals (i.e. numerals that are not composed of other numerals – though some are composed of other recognizable morphemes) for ‘1’ through ‘5’, ‘10’, and ‘20’. The system above ‘20’ is vigesimal. Nowadays, especially for higher numbers, Bahasa Indonesia numerals are usually used, so most of the material below is based on (at times rather forced) elicitation.

The simple numerals are: ‘1’ *mbéy*, ‘2’ *be*, ‘3’ *naming*, ‘4’ *keri mbéy* (literally ‘bunch one’), ‘5’ *me si* (literally ‘hand other’); ‘10’ *me be* (literally ‘hand two’); ‘20’ *do mbéy* (literally ‘man one’) or *do wa mbéy* (literally ‘man body one’). It should be noted that the usual counting aid is to lower the raised fingers (and not, as in Anglo-Saxon cultures, to raise the lowered fingers) for the first ten, then to count the second ten along the knuckles of the lowered fingers furthest from the fingertips, and the Tepera teen numerals make explicit reference to the knuckles – the vigesimal base does not involve ‘toe counting’.

The numerals ‘6’ through ‘9’ are formed on the pattern ‘5’ *su na x* where *x* is the difference between the number in question and 5. In this expression, *su* is literally ‘side’

and *na* is the relative postposition (see the section on possession below). Thus: ‘6’ *me si su na mbéy*, ‘7’ *me si su na be*, ‘8’ *me si su na naming*, ‘9’ *me si su na keru mbéy*.

The teens are formed on the pattern ‘10’ *me toki x pere*, where *x* is the difference between the number in question and 10. The literal meaning of *me* is ‘hand’, that of *toki* is ‘knuckle (furthest from finger tip)’, while *pere* is the comitative postposition ‘with’. Thus: ‘11’ *me be me toki mbéy pere*, ‘19’ *me be me toki me si su na keru mbéy pere*.

The even tens (i.e. the twenties), at least up to ‘100’ (I consider elicited forms over 100 highly unreliable), simply replace the *mbéy* ‘one’ of *do (wa) mbéy* ‘20’ with the appropriate factor of 20, i.e. ‘40’ *do (wa) be*, ‘60’ *do (wa) naming*, ‘80’ *do (wa) keru mbéy*, ‘100’ *do (wa) me si*. This system probably continues up to at least ‘200’, for which I consider the elicited form *do (wa) me be* reasonably reliable.

Numbers between the exact twenties are expressed as *do (wa) x y pere*, where *x* is the factor of 20 closest to and lower than the number in question, and *y* is the difference between the number in question and this factor of 20. Thus: ‘21’ *do (wa) mbéy mbéy pere*, ‘30’ *do (wa) mbéy me be pere*. Where this formula might lead one to expect two occurrences of *pere* in a row (i.e. for numbers between an odd ten and an even ten, expressed as so many twenties plus a number in the teens), one of the occurrences of *pere* is simply dropped, e.g. ‘31’ *do (wa) mbéy me be me toki mbéy pere*.

It will be seen that even fairly low numbers have quite complex expressions in Tepera.

Within the noun phrase, the head noun (and following adjective, if any) is usually (though not obligatorily) separated from the numeral by the word *seréy* ‘quantity, so much’, e.g. *awe (poy) seréy naming* ‘three (good) birds’. The word *seréy* functions in this way rather like a classifier in many other languages – except that Tepera would have only one “class”!

Pronouns

The Tepera pronominal system distinguishes four persons: first person exclusive (*de*, which excludes the addressee), first person inclusive (*é*, which includes the addressee), second person (*we*), third person (*ne*). There is no distinction of number (although the first person inclusive necessarily refers to a set containing at least two members). For Mr. Jakarimilena, the distinction between *de* and *é* is clearly one of exclusion versus inclusion, and not one of number; it is possible that this is a recent development, since some earlier wordlists give *de* and *é* as singular and plural respectively, and Cowan (1965: 16) suggests that the innovatory exclusive/inclusive distinction in Sentani may reflect the influence of neighboring Austronesian languages.

Pronouns are different from other noun phrases in the expression of the comitative relation and in the expression of possession.

Possession

The expression of possession, in a broad sense, is one of the most complex areas of noun phrase internal syntax in Tepera, involving some idiosyncrasies not found elsewhere in the language: special forms for pronouns quite distinct from those found for nouns; prefixed possessed forms for some kinship terms (although Tepera seems otherwise to be exclusively suffixing, especially in its inflectional morphology).

For possessor nouns, the usual marker is the postposition *kena*, which I gloss as GEN (genitive), e.g. *di detero kena yoku* ‘that person’s dog’.

In addition, the postposition *na* is sometimes found with a possessor noun. However, in all these cases the idea is not so much possession in the strict sense as a more general relation, such as would often be expressed in English by means of a compound noun, e.g. *naw na ka* ‘sea fish’, *merway na ka* ‘river fish’. I therefore gloss *na*, in all its functions (see also the discussion of possessive pronouns and of clause combining) as REL (relative). Incidentally, the name *Jakarimilena*, i.e. *yakari miré na*, is literally ‘Yakari female REL’, i.e. ‘of (descended from) a Yakari woman’.

For possessor pronouns, however, *na* is the basic marker, e.g. *we na yoku* ‘your dog’. With pronouns, *kena* seems to be excluded (although phrases like *é be* ‘we two, you and I’, consisting of more than just a pronoun, function like nouns, with the possessor form *é be kena*).

In addition, pronouns have a special possessive (POSS) form which is clearly inflectional. The full form consists basically of following the pronoun by its own initial consonant followed by *éy*, i.e. first person exclusive *deréy* (with a *d ~ r* alternation for which there is some independent evidence, e.g. the common first person verb suffix *-(V)re*), first person inclusive *éyéy* (with *y* as a hiatus breaker, as in verb morphology; there is, of course, no initial consonant to be reduplicated), second person *wewéy*, third person *nenéy*. Except for the first person inclusive, there is also a shorter form lacking the *eC* sequence: *déy*, *wéy*, *néy*.

In general, the relative and possessive forms of pronouns are interchangeable, but the possessive form seems to give greater emphasis to the possession, i.e. ‘my own dog’ rather than just ‘my dog’. These leads to an interesting interpretative difference between *de na jéy* and *deréy jéy*, both in a sense ‘my children’. Since the Tepera kinship system is classificatory, *jeý* as a kinship term refers not only to one’s own biological children, but also to the children of one’s siblings of the same sex and, more generally, all members of the same clan one generation younger than ego other than those for whom more specific kinship terms exist. The expression *de na jéy* would therefore normally be taken to include many nephews and nieces, while *deréy jéy* would be more likely to be taken to mean one’s own biological offspring.

For a number of kinship terms, there are special forms for possession by a pronoun (other than the first person inclusive). Not all kinship terms are included – there are no such forms, for instance, for (*me*)*may* ‘father’, *naméng* ‘mother’, *jéy* ‘child’. (One might argue that *jéy* is not strictly a kinship term, since it also the general word for ‘child’, i.e. ‘nonadult human’; however, *memay* and *naméng* are clearly kinship terms, while *do* and *miré* do have special possessed forms in the meaning ‘husband’ and ‘wife’ respectively, although these are also general words for ‘man, male’ and ‘woman, female’.)

The possessed forms recognized by Mr. Jakarimilena are given in the following table. The English glosses are approximate, corresponding fairly well in prototypical instances, but less well in peripheral instances, given the classificatory nature of the Tepera kinship system. Questioned forms and blanks indicate logically possible combinations that Mr. Jakarimilena considers either doubtful or impossible:

Meaning	Citation	1st person	2nd person	3rd person
grandchild	koti	doti	woti	noti
husband	do	démbero	wémbero	némbero
wife	miré	'démbiré	'wémbiré	'némbiré
elder sibling	aka	deka	weka	neka
brother (of woman)	—	dénung	wénung	nénung
sister	méngke	deméng	weméng	neméng
grandfather	sese	?dese	?wese	nese
grandmother	kéméng	?déngken	?wéngken	néngken
greatgrandparent	kasi	dekasi	wekasi	nekasi
father’s sister	éneng	déneng	wéneng	néneng
mother’s brother	(we)way	—	—	newaw
parent-in-law	?san	desan	wesan	nesan
sibling-in-law	meso	démeso	wémeso	némeso
friend	deko	déndeko	wéndeko	néndeko

These forms clearly involve prefixing *d-*, *w-*, *n-*, sometimes followed by *é* (as in the possessive pronouns?), then followed by a (usually abbreviated) form of the noun stem, but equally clearly a number of idiosyncrasies are involved. But note that for a given lexical item, all possessed nouns are formed in the same way.

Alongside forms like *noti*, Mr. Jakarimilena also accepts the regular phrase *ne na/nenéy koti*. Where the possessor is a noun rather than a pronoun, one can have either the noun followed by the possessed noun, or the noun followed by *kena* followed by the citation form of the noun, e.g. *kuru noti* or *kuru kena koti* ‘the teacher’s grandchild’.

For other noun possessives, Mr. Jakarimilena also accepts the sequence noun + possessive pronoun (or pronoun + REL) + noun, e.g. *kuru nenéy jéy* or *kuru ne na jéy* ‘the teacher’s child’.

Benefactives

Because of their unusual properties and problems in their analysis, it is worth devoting a separate section to benefactives. The basic expression of the benefactive (BEN) relation is the postposition *tena* (perhaps composed of *te* and *na*), as in:

- (8) *ne miré ne na jéy miré tena mayong te dow-k-u.*
the female (s)he REL child female BEN dress OBJ take-AOR-3SG
'The woman bought a dress for her daughter.'

This sentence illustrates the normal word order, with the benefactive phrase preceding the direct object. If the benefactive phrase is moved to any other position (i.e. after the direct object, or away from the direct object), then the object postposition *te* must be added to the benefactive phrase, i.e. *ne miré mayong te ne na jéy miré tena te dowku*. Thus, if the benefactive does not immediately precede the direct object, it must agree with it in case.

This might seem to suggest that the benefactive and the direct object are a single noun phrase, with the structure [...]_{BEN...}_{OBJ}. As long as the benefactive remains part of the larger noun phrase, it does not agree with the head noun, but once it is moved to some other position, it must agree. For a similar situation with relative clauses, see the section on clause combining below.

But if the sequence of benefactive and direct object were indeed a single noun phrase, then one would expect this noun phrase to be able to occur in other syntactic positions, i.e. one would expect sentences like:

- (9) **da detero tena miyé re me-y-are.*
this person BEN house ABL come-IMP-1SG
'I came from the house that is destined for this man.'

However, this sentence is judged unequivocally ungrammatical, suggesting that the benefactive is not an attribute within a larger noun phrase. Faced with this conflicting evidence, I am not able to propose a definitive analysis.

Other nominal markers and categories

Number: Tepera nouns and pronouns have no grammatical category of number. This is unusual (but not quite unique) among the languages of the world for pronouns. For human nouns (but not pronouns) it is possible to indicate plurality by the postposed markers *po* or *bera*, but a noun phrase with no marker can be interpreted as having any number. Dual number can be indicated by adding the numeral *be* 'two' to the end of any noun phrase, including pronouns, e.g. *miré be* 'two women', *de be* 'we two (excluding you)', *é be* 'we two, you and I'. Especially for the pronouns, it is usual (though not

obligatory) to indicate dual number in this way. It should be noted, however, that verb agreement does show an obligatory singular/dual/plural opposition, so that the number of a noun phrase is often deducible from its agreement properties.

Gender/class: Tepera has no gender or class system. The sex of nouns without inherent sex specification can be expressed overtly by placing *do* ‘male’ or *miré* ‘female’ after the noun, e.g. *jéy do* ‘son’, *kuru miré* ‘woman teacher’.

Miscellaneous

kare: After a noun phrase, this means ‘what about X?’

yenate (probably *ye na te*): After a noun phrase, this means ‘it is X that can...’, e.g.:

(10) *de yenate dimi+semo te dimi-nde.*
we yenate song OBJ sing-PRS.1DU
‘It is we two who can sing.’

mo: After a noun phrase, this means ‘only X’; its scope is the preceding noun phrase.

rati: After a noun phrase, this means ‘also X, X too’; its scope is the preceding noun phrase.

tere: After a noun, this means ‘a real X’; after an adjective, it means ‘very’.

way, méng: These are often added after the names of, respectively, males and females. The form *way* is clearly related to (*we*)*way* ‘mother’s brother’, while *méng* is related to *méngke* ‘sister’.

ko: After a noun, this refers to an activity connected with that noun. Apparently this form can only occur with a following locational postposition, referring to engagement in (locative), going to (directional), or coming from (source) the activity in question; the whole construction is a nonverbal predicate. Thus, from *awe* ‘bird’ we have: *de awe ko ne* ‘I am hunting birds’ (‘I am birding’), *de awe ko te* ‘I am going (in order) to hunt birds’, *de awe ko re* ‘I am coming from hunting birds’.

Verb morphology

The morphology of the verb is by far the most complex area of Tepera morphology. The approach followed below is primarily descriptive; for a more abstract phonological analysis, reference may be made to Collier & Gregerson (1985).

The verb stem itself is never a separate word, but always requires at least one suffix. Nearly all verb stems end in a vowel. Some verb stems end in *w*, e.g. *dow-* ‘take’. One of

the suppletive stems of the verb ‘go’ is zero \emptyset – the other stem is *é-*); this verb is, incidentally, the only example of suppletion of which I am aware (the verb ‘come’ shares the same suppletion, differing from ‘go’ only in the addition of initial *m(e)-*, perhaps a prefix).

The tense-mood-aspect (TAM) system makes the following distinctions: present (PRS) (with no aspectual distinction; effectively, it is only imperfective); imperfect (IMP) (imperfective past); aorist (AOR) (perfective past); future I (FUTI) (imperfective future); future II (FUTII) (perfective future); conditional (COND) (with no tense or aspect distinctions). Apart from the conditional, all other TAMs are indicative.

The use of the aorist deserves much more investigation. While all instances of the aorist are indeed perfective past, there are many instances in texts where one might have expected a form with perfective past meaning (e.g. in the narration of sequenced events), but where nonetheless the imperfect is used. For the basic verbs of motion ‘go’ (\emptyset -) and ‘come’ (*me-*) the aorist is never used in its literal sense; the aorist of these verbs can be used immediately preceding some other verb to provide a kind of serial verb construction (‘went/came and V-ed’). For yet other verbs, the aorist seems to have been lexicalized (referring specifically to the total completion of an action), and it may well be that overall much of the analysis of the aorist belongs in the lexicon rather than in the grammar.

For future time reference, my materials have primarily the future I, with only occasional instances of the future II. I do not have enough examples to establish the precise difference between the two futures, and the definitions given above reflect the analysis for corresponding forms in Yewena by Collier & Gregerson (1986).

In general, the TAM morphology is fusional, as can be seen from the paradigms below – moreover, TAM morphology is sometimes fused with subject agreement morphology. The main exception is the imperfect, formed by adding *-yo* to the stem, then adding the same person-number suffixes as in the present.

There seems to be no special imperative, second person forms from other TAMs being used instead. The most neutral imperative uses the future I. A polite imperative uses the conditional; for the singular there is an alternative form in *-ipoy*, e.g. *meko-ypoy*, apparently the conditional stem.

For polarity, the affirmative is not marked morphologically, while the negative requires the suffix *-ipay*. Stem-final *e* and *i* are deleted before this suffix. Other vowels remain, but the initial segment of the suffix is desyllabified to give *-ypay*. Examples are: *meko-ypay* ‘not make’, *t-ipay* (from *te-*) ‘not see’. The negative of ‘go’ is simply *ipay*, since the zero-stem of this verb is used here. The most surprising characteristic of the negative is that it involves the neutralization of all other verb categories: thus *meko-ypay* is the negative equivalent of all TAM and all person-number forms in the affirmative of *meko-*.

However, negative forms do seem to be verbal rather than nonverbal predicates, since they do not cooccur with *neke-* ‘stay’ as an overt marker of verb categories.

All affirmative verbs agree in person and number with their subject. There is a threeway number distinction (singular (SG), dual (DU), plural (PL)), which is obligatory (even though there is no number category in noun phrases). There is also a threeway person distinction (first, second, third), with no distinction between exclusive and inclusive first persons. The overall distinction is thus nineway, although there are some instances of accidental syncretism/homophony (different for different TAMs). In conjunction with the rich verb agreement system, it is possible to omit unstressed pronouns; at least in discourse, it is also possible to omit pronouns whose reference is retrievable from context even if there is no agreement with that noun phrase position.

There is also some encoding of features of the object in some verbs: the precise details are complex, and seem to be partly lexicalized. First, for some verbal concepts different lexical items are used depending on the number of the object, e.g. ‘beat’ is *to-* when one entity is affected but *tutu-* when more than one entity is affected. Collier & Gregerson (1985) note that in Yewena, the number of the object is encoded in the aorist of many verbs by means of the morpheme preceding the aorist marker *-k-*: singular *-mbe-*, dual *-ke-*, plural *-pe-* (although for other verbs these suffixes quantify actions rather than objects). For Tepera, I have not been able to elicit any forms with *-ke-*, while some combinations of person and number of the subject seem to require specifically either *-mbe-* or *-pe-*. For some combinations of person and number of the subject, there are variants with *-mbe-* and *-pe-*, but they do not seem to correlate systematically with the number of the object.

For yet other verbs, there are specific suffixes indicating the person-number of the object. The distinction is not, however, the expected nineway system, since person distinctions are not made in the nonsingular. The basic forms of these suffixes are: first singular *-t-*, second singular *-w-*, third singular *-n-*, dual *-p-*, plural *-m-*. In some cases, these are added at the end of the unsuffixed form, in which case they have a following vowel *e* and optionally a final nasal; if the unsuffixed form ends in *e*, this is dropped, thus, from *sane-yo-we* ‘say-IMP-3SG’ we get: *sane-yo-w-te(ng)* ‘he told me’, *sane-yo-w-we(ng)* ‘he told you’, *sane-yo-w-ne(ng)* ‘he told him’, *sane-yo-w-pe(ng)* ‘he told two people’, *sane-yo-w-me(ng)* ‘he told more than two people’. In other cases, however, the object prefixes precede the subject agreement suffixes, or perhaps more accurately are inserted into them, e.g. *i-* ‘give’: *i-k-a-w-are* ‘I gave to you’, *i-k-a-n-are* ‘I gave to him’, *i-k-a-p-are* ‘I gave to you/them two’, *i-k-a-m-are* ‘I gave to you/them all’. In these forms of ‘give’, the subject agreement suffix is basically *-are*, but the *-a* preceding the object marker seems also to belong to the subject agreement suffix, cf. *i-k-é-t-é* ‘you gave to me’, *i-k-é-n-é* ‘you gave to him’, where *-é* is the second person singular subject agreement suffix. For some verbs, the occurrence of these object markers is in complementary distribution with overt objects (i.e. *sane-yo-we* is used if the object is expressed as a noun phrase), while for others the object suffix is obligatory even in the presence of an overt object – this is

the case with ‘give’, so that ‘I gave (it) to the woman’ is *ne miré te i-k-a-n-are*. Note that in the hierarchy of objects for controlling object agreement, indirect objects (recipients) take precedence over direct objects (patients). Finally, some transitive verbs seem to lack object agreement completely.

Verb paradigms

Below, the various forms of the verb *meko-* ‘make’ are given, as examples of the most productive kind of verb morphologically.

Present	Singular	Dual	Plural
1st	mek-are	meko-nde	mek-a-nde
2nd	meko-y-é	meko-we	mek-a-we
3rd	meko-w(n)e	meko-y(n)e	mek-a-y(n)e

Note here and below the pervasive effect of the rule deleting one vowel before another. If the verb stem happens to end in *a*, e.g. *teka-* ‘split’, the dual and plural forms will of course merge, e.g. *tekande* ‘we two/all split’. In the second person singular, this rule is bled by an alternative means of avoiding hiatus: insertion of *y*. Some verbs also show the effect of *a* apophony: underlying /a/ preceded by a consonant shifts to *e* if there is an *a* in the next following syllable: thus *sane-* ‘say’ conjugates as follows: *sen-are*, *sane-y-é*, *sane-we*, *sane-nde* (etc., through the dual), *sen-a-nde* (etc., through the plural). This apophony does not effect word-initial /a/, thus from ‘eat’ we have *an-are* ‘I eat’. In both elicitation and texts, forms with and without *n* were given for third person.

Imperfect	Singular	Dual	Plural
1st	meko-y-are	meko-yo-nde	meko-y-a-nde
2nd	meko-y-é	meko-yo-we	meko-y-a-we
3rd	meko-yo-w(n)e	meko-yo-y(n)e	meko-y-a-y(n)e

Note that in the second person singular, in the imperfect the *y* is the imperfect suffix, while in the present it is a hiatus breaker.

Future I	Singular	Dual	Plural
1st	meko-tere	mek-are	meko-mare
2nd	meko-we	meko-pe	meko-mbe
3rd	meko-n(d)e	meko-néye	meko-naye

In the third person dual and plural, *meko-néynde* and *meko-naynde* are apparently also possible. The second person of the future I is also used as an imperative, although there are more polite ways of expressing the imperative using the conditional.

Aorist	Singular	Dual	Plural
1st	meko-pe-k-are	meko-mbe-k-o	mek-a-mbe-k-o
2nd	meko-pe-k-é	meko-pe-k-o	mek-a-pe-k-o
3rd	meko-pe-k-o	meko-y-pe-k-o	mek-a-y-pe-k-o

The basic suffix marking the aorist is *-k*. Not all verbs have the “labial” suffix *-pe-/-mbe-*; as an example of one that does not, we cite the aorist of *yosu-* ‘descend’ – it should be noted, however, that I am uncertain of several of these forms:

Aorist	Singular	Dual	Plural
1st	yosu-k-are	yosu-k-ende	yosu-k-a-nde
2nd	yosu-k-é	yosu-k-é-we	yosu-k-a-we
3rd	yosu-k-u	yosu-k-é-ye	yosu-k-a-ye

Possibly, the third person plural should be *yosi-k-i*.

Future II	Singular	Dual	Plural
1st	meko-te-mbo-nde	mek-a-mbo-nde	meko-m-a-mbo-nde
2nd	meko-po-nde	meko-po-pe	meko-mbo-mbe
3rd	meko-ne-mbo-nde	meko-n-éy-mbo-nde	meko-n-ay-mbo-nde

All forms with the suffix *-nde* have an alternative in *-ne*.

Conditional	Singular	Dual	Plural
1st	meko-y-po-y-e	meko-mbo-we	mek-a-mbo-we
2nd	meko-y-po-y-mé	meko-po-we	mek-a-po-we
3rd	meko-po-we	meko-y-po-ye	mek-a-y-po-we

The second person of the conditional is used as a polite imperative. Note that the *-y* of *-y-po* seems to be underlyingly *-i*, and like the negative suffix it deletes stem-final *e*, *i* of the verb, e.g. *an-i-po-y-e* ‘I would eat’ (from *ane-* ‘eat’).

Clause combining

In Tepera, it is possible simply to juxtapose clauses without any overt indication of the relationship among them.

Equally, however, one can chain clauses together such that only one is an independent clause, the others being marked by the relative (REL) postposition *na* after their verb, plus another postposition making explicit the semantic link between the two clauses. (Final (*n*)*e* is dropped after a semivowel before *na*, but otherwise there are no special dependent verb forms.)

The basic relation of time when (i.e. simultaneity) uses the locative postposition *ne*, as in:

- (11) de ye dimi+semo te dimi-y-are na ne,
 I INST song OBJ sing-IMP-1SG REL LOC
 di detero te pene-y-are.
 that person OBJ hit-IMP-1SG
 ‘When I was singing a song, I was hitting that person.’

To indicate a succession of events, the postposition *kare* is used:

- (12) de ye mi-y-are na kare,
 I INST come-IMP-1SG REL after
 di detero de te pene-yo-w-te.
 that person I OBJ hit-IMP-3SG-1SGO
 ‘After I came here, that person hit me.’

There is no special form to indicate ‘before’, rather the locative postposition *ne* is used with the negative of the verb, i.e. ‘before I came’ is literally ‘when I didn’t come’:

- (13) de ye m-ipay na ne,
 I INSTR come-NEG REL LOC
 di detero de te pene-yo-w-te.
 that person I OBJ hit-IMP-3SG-1SGO
 ‘Before I came here, that person hit me.’

To express purpose, the future tense is followed by the postposition sequence *na te* (REL OBJ):

- (14) di detero to te ane-ne na te,
 that person coconut OBJ eat-FUTI.3SG REL OBJ
 da pe te me-yo-we.
 this place OBJ come-IMP-3SG
 ‘That person came here in order to eat the coconut.’

Cause can be expressed using the postpositions *sate* or *pote*:

- (15) de ye semo te i-tere na sate/pote,
 I INST letter OBJ give-FUTI.1SG REL because,
 di detero da pe te me-yo-we.
 that person this place OBJ come-IMP-3SG
 ‘The man came here because I wanted to give him the letter.’

Different nominalizations or adjectivalizations of the clause give sentences with similar interpretations:

(21) [de ye to-pe-k-are na] detero jayapura ne neke-we.
 I INST hit-Ø-AOR-1SG REL person Jayapura LOC stay-PRS.3SG
 ‘The person that I hit lives in Jayapura.’

(22) [de ye semo te i-k-a-n-are na]
 I INST letter OBJ give-AOR-Ø-3SGO-1SG REL
 detero jayapura ne neke-we.
 person Jayapura LOC stay-PRS.3SG
 ‘The person to whom I gave the letter lives in Jayapura.’

(23) [é ye nek-ande na] miyé dére.
 1.INCL INST stay-PRS.1PL REL house big
 ‘The house in which we live is big.’

When the noun relativized functions as possessor within a noun phrase in the relative clause, then a pronoun resuming the noun relativized must appear in the relative clause; I have examples of this kind only in elicited material:

(24) [ne na yoku te de ye to-pe-k-are na] detero
 he REL dog OBJ I INST hit-Ø-AOR-1SG REL person
 jayapura ne neke-we.
 Jayapura LOC stay-PRS.3SG
 ‘The person whose dog I hit lives in Jayapura.’

It is also possible for a relative clause to appear after its head noun, or even to be separated from it, but in this case the relative clause must take the same postpositional marker as the head noun:

(25) ne detero te [Jayapura ne neke-we na te] de ye to-pe-k-are.
 the person OBJ Jayapura LOC stay-PRS.3SG REL OBJ I INST hit-Ø-AOR-1SG
 ‘I hit the person who lives in Jayapura.’

In this alternative construction, it is possible that we have two noun phrases in apposition, the second being headless (i.e. roughly ‘the person, the one who lives in Jayapura’). A further piece of evidence in favor of this is the occurrence of the demonstrative *ne* in this second version (but not in the first).

For all instances of clause combining where there is a clear distinction between subordinate and main clause, the verb of the subordinate clause precedes the verb of the main clause. In general, the whole subordinate clause precedes the whole of the main clause (except in relative clauses, where the subordinate clause is normally adjacent to its head noun), although the subordinate clause can also be inserted into the main clause, as in some of the examples above.

Borrowed conjunctions from Bahasa Indonesia, in clause-initial position, are not infrequent in the texts, for instance the causal conjunction *sebab* and the relative clause introducer *yang*.

Abbreviations

1,2,3	grammatical persons	INCL	inclusive
ABL	ablative	INST	instrumental
AOR	aorist	LOC	locative
BEN	benefactive	NEG	negative
COM	comitative	O	object index
COND	conditional	OBJ	object
DU	dual	PL	plural
FUTI	future I	PRS	present
FUTII	future II	REL	relative
GEN	genitive	SG	singular
IMP	imperfect	TOP	topic

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[Map source: Jakarimilena 1979]